

THE ROLE OF RURAL TOURISM IN MODERN TOURISM TRENDS

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Annotatsiya. Maqolada O'zbekistonda agroturizm va qishloq turizmini rivojlantirish imkoniyatlari va bosqichlari hamda uning tarkibiy qismlari to'liq yoritilgan. Mamlakatda qishloq turizmining afzalliklaridan foydalanish imkoniyatlari.

Kalit so'zlar: qishloq turizmi, agroturizm, turistik mehmonxonalar, ekoturizm, ziyorat turizmi, ta'lim turizmi, tibbiy turizm, etnoturizm.

Аннотация. В статье подробно описаны возможности и этапы развития сельского туризма в Узбекистане, а также его составляющие. Возможности использования преимуществ сельского туризма в стране.

Ключевые слова: сельский туризм, агротуризм, туристские гостиницы, экотуризм, паломнический туризм, познавательный туризм, медицинский туризм, этнотуризм.

Abstract. The article describes in detail the possibilities and stages of the development of rural tourism in Uzbekistan, as well as its components. Opportunities to take advantage of rural tourism in the country.

Keywords: rural tourism, agritourism, tourist hotels, ecotourism, pilgrimage tourism, educational tourism, medical tourism, ethnotourism.

INTRODUCTION

Rural tourism in Uzbekistan has received an impetus to development against the background of changes in the structure of tourism demand caused by the closure of borders due to pandemic factors. This type of tourism in our country has a good prospect to attract domestic and, with the opening of borders, foreign tourists. Russia has inexhaustible opportunities to promote rural tourism, offering interesting places and rural farms that have the resource and desire to develop tourism.

The purpose of this study is: on the basis of consideration of modern trends and the role of rural tourism industry for socio-economic development of Uzbekistan, to formulate possible directions of development of the sector under consideration in relation to the economy of our country.

Attention to the issues of rural tourism development is explained by its importance for the progress of the economy and society of the country and its regions. In particular, it should be emphasized:

- Providing accommodation, recreation and catering services to rural tourists contributes to the growth of employment (secondary employment including) of the rural population, prevents them from moving to the cities;

- rural tourism industry offers, as a rule, inexpensive recreation. Tourists are organized accommodation in rural houses, acquaintance with the farms of farmers (keeping birds, animals, cultivation of garden and vegetable plants), various formats of organizing recreation in nature (hunting, fishing, picking mushrooms, berries, horseback riding, sledding, etc.);

- rural tourism familiarizes vacationers with rural work, for example, mowing hay, participation in harvesting, feeding animals, birds, milking cows, going out for grazing, etc.;
- rural tourism directly contributes to the development of backward non-industrialized regions, providing an opportunity for income generation through the interest of urban residents in the countryside and traditional ways of life.

Material and research methods

Uzbekistan has serious opportunities to develop rural tourism, offering as objects interesting natural landscapes and colorful rural farms, providing resources and willingness to receive tourists.

For such areas of already operating business as farming, including breeding of domestic animals, crop production, farming, rural tourism will be an additional source of income. For the state rural tourism will form an additional basis for the development of investment attractiveness [1]. Table 1 outlines the role of rural tourism for the population, business representatives and the state as a whole.

Table 1. The role of rural tourism in the modern economy

Nature of the effect	For rural population	For business	For the state
Employment	Growth of employment, including secondary employment	Increasing the human resource potential of businesses in tourism through the involvement of rural residents in employment in the tourism industry	Reduction of budgetary expenditures on employment policies
Economic incentives	Generating additional income	Receiving additional income	Increase in tax revenues to the budget
Infrastructure	Increase in the comfort of living in rural areas, including through the progress of local infrastructure	Creation of additional conditions for investment	Infrastructural development
Non-economic effects	Moral satisfaction from the realization of the need for personal growth	Information support and assistance of the concerned authorities of tourist regions and the state	Balanced system of citizens' settlement
Market promotion	Development of local communities	Promotion of environmentally friendly products and services of local producers	Promotion of regional brands and growth of investment attractiveness of the

			region
Reduction of socio economic risks	Preservation of traditional rural settlements and customary ways of life	Commercialization of traditional rural crafts and trades, including those that are declining	Preservation of cultural and historical heritage
	Involvement of the population in business and cultural ties	Reduction of the influence of seasonal factors on rural business	Socio-economic development of territories

The village is historically a treasure trove of traditional national ways of life and culture. However, unlike urban social infrastructure, rural infrastructure is represented by a narrower list of objects, and in some regions it is even in a dilapidated state or is absent.

Loans for rural businesses are often not supported by the credit system, have unattractive conditions and are quite expensive. In addition, the labor market in rural areas is much more modest and incomes are lower. [2].

In order to achieve the goals it is necessary to diversify the rural economy, support farms, develop crafts and traditional forms of activity of the rural population, search for alternative forms of employment and self-employment in rural areas. Rural tourism seems to be one of the promising means of solving these problems.

Over the past eight years, there has been a trend towards the development of rural tourism. State regional and municipal programs have been developed and implemented.

It should be noted that the emergence in late 2019 of a hotbed of a new coronavirus infection Covid-19 in China with its subsequent spread to other countries and the declaration of a pandemic by the World Health Organization reversed the trend of sustainable development of the tourism industry in 2020. It is obvious that in the post-pandemic realities it is necessary to search for new drivers of industry development.

Statistics Agency: In January-February, 974.2 thousand foreign citizens came to Uzbekistan for tourism purposes. Compared to the same period last year, their number increased by 103.5 thousand people or 11.9%. Among the countries from where the most tourists came for two months of this year:

- Tajikistan - 363.4 thousand;
- Kyrgyzstan - 291.1 thousand;
- Kazakhstan - 155.9 thousand;
- Russia - 77.9 thousand;
- Turkmenistan - 20.2 thousand;
- Turkey - 14.3 thousand;
- India - 7.0 thousand;
- China - 5.5 thousand;
- South Korea - 5.4 thousand;
- Belarus - 2.2 thousand;
- Other countries - 31.3 thousand .

Against this background, domestic tourism, in particular rural tourism (also called "agrarian", we consider these categories as identical) has a significant attractiveness, including investment.

In a pandemic economy, rural domestic tourism has the undoubted advantage of maintaining social distance, which makes its development possible even in conditions of rather strict anti-epidemic restrictions. Rural tourism is carried out in the destinations that have a known lower population density and are under the influence of natural healing factors" [3]. [3].

RESULTS OF THE STUDY AND THEIR DISCUSSION

Rural tourism has good prospects to become one of the drivers of postpandemic recovery of all tourism industry.

Unfortunately, until now the development of rural tourism in our country has not been given due attention. The development of rural tourism in the territory of Uzbekistan and its regions requires the solution of a number of serious problems.

First of all, it is the formation of infrastructure. Rural tourism infrastructure includes: a network of roads and communications; communication; power grids; water and gas supply; a set of tourist routes; areas for recreation and entertainment; tourism transportation network; information network. One of the steps could be the inclusion of the construction and reconstruction of rural roads, especially access roads to rural settlements, in the national project "Safe and Quality Highways" and in the state program "Development of the Transport System".

The development of rural tourism will also be facilitated by ensuring the level of quality of services in accordance with the best international practices. Without an increase in the quality of services, rural tourism will have to be satisfied with some narrow niches of clients and the most inexpensive price category. Therefore, there is an urgent need to pay attention to the problem of improving the overall quality of training of personnel engaged in rural tourism and, especially important - the exchange of best practices and training in successful centers of rural tourism. Only in this case we can count on progress and sustainable development of rural tourism as an industry, and not turning it into a disposable product with declared, but really lacking characteristics.

Assistance at the regional level in the formation of rural tourism services as a complex offer. In this case, the complexity of rural tourism service implies:

- 1) Providing tourists with information about the object of recreation in the village;
- 2) The possibility of organizing a transfer to the place of recreation in the village, or providing the tourist with information about the types of transport to get to the place independently;
- 3) Providing the tourist with the necessary information on the spot upon arrival (in particular about possible types of recreation, objects, entertainment, activities, recreational events, etc.);
- 4) Provision of accommodation and catering services in the rural destination;
- 5) Leisure activities: entertainment, animation, socializing, hiking, master classes to introduce crafts, active rest, etc.;
- 6) Organization of departure and return transfer of tourists from the place of recreation;
- 7) Providing the work of feedback channels on the results of the rural tour and targeted advertising aimed at repeat visits [4].

The considered sequence of services can be implemented both by one farmer (entrepreneur), and be entrusted to several rural farms, or interested residents of the whole rural

settlement, so it is necessary to consider the issues of promoting self-organization and cooperation of farms in the organization of rural tourism services.

CONCLUSIONS

It should be noted that the peculiarity of the nascent Russian rural tourism is that it was formed "from below" - without continuous significant participation of the central governing state structures, respectively, without the presence of an existing national program and financial support. In connection with the current pandemic and increasing interest of tourists in rural tourism, federal and local authorities should use the emerging opportunities and take measures to support and develop it.

The development of this segment of the tourism industry will have a positive impact on the progress of the rural economy and improving the quality of life of the rural population, will be an additional support for farming and create opportunities for alternative forms of employment and self-employment in rural areas, will help to complement the infrastructure, improve the level of service, provide the village with additional sources of income.

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